

BUDDHIST WISDOM

Dr. Paula Arizpe.

BUDDHISM is about Padmasambhava's or Guru Rinpoche's nature and teachings.

He was born in India took the Buddha-dharma to Tibet and continues to be a source of inspiration, in this sense, it is said, he is still alive. In the Christian tradition, he would have been considered a saint. Saints are considered to have direct communication with God to the extent that some fall in a sort of rapture that enables them to make promises to the people. They are also considered to be models of superior consciousness and full development.

For Buddhism, spirituality, is something quite different, it is a non-theistic approach, in which an extrinsic divinity is not present. Spirituality consists in an inner awakening which has nothing to do with the external plane.

In a Buddhist context, Padmasambhava, or even an exceptional being as Buddha himself are the testimony that a simple and common, disoriented, human being has the capacity to awaken, to build enough courage to be awakened by whatever fortuitous event. Pain, suffering, affliction, and chaos, are part of the life that shakes him up, as to become awoken.

Numbly the person asks itself: Who am I? What am I? Why does all of this happen?

So deep down he finds something within himself that is asking these questions, something intelligent that is not confused as the rest of him.

This happens IN OUR LIFE. We feel confused –or we think of it that way- but this confusion is pointing to something worthwhile to reflect upon, the questions posed when sunk in confusion are authentic and potent because they dig deep inside like: Who is this, that is asking these questions? THIS is non-theistic spirituality in full extension. Once we are clear what and who we are, a new question arises: how are we going to apply these new discoveries in our daily life?

The first option:

- 1) We can live accordingly to what we would like to be,
- or
- 2) Try to be what we actually are.

1) to pretend everything is fine when we know it is not. "Let's think everything is O.K." is called **spiritual materialism** in the Buddhist tradition, it is simply unrealistic. Spiritual materialism would be anything –coming from any tradition- which proposes to relate to any God or divinity. When we feel in contact with the GOOD, we feel happy, we feel fascinated and feel liberated and just let life go on. Then a second element to reinforce this spiritual materialism is added when we link that which we know not, or do not understand with citations of different sacred books to name the ineffable, which is beyond (our) words and (our) comprehension. Therefore, we relate our disability to understand what is happening to us with the ineffable or inexpressible: in this way, our own ignorance becomes the greatest discovery! And we make this discovery coincide with some doctrinal hypothesis or any other interpretation of a sacred text.

Before, we knew nothing, now we "know" something that we don't know what it is, and more over cannot be described with words, concepts, or ideas but we have learned that we can deform ourselves until we transform in something "good", therefore, we have a starting point: to take our confusion and in a direct and conscious way, turn it into a free state of confusion. What is leading us through this path is precisely the search for pleasure: spiritual pleasure. By doing so, we affirm that pleasure is beyond knowledge, because in fact we have not the slightest idea of what sort of pleasure is acquired in this way! So, we really do not know what we are doing in the spiritual level,

nevertheless as the initial questions of what and who we are that underlie our feeling of nothingness are wiped away. As these primal questions are overcome, our spiritual conviction becomes a certainty.

Having suppressed, in this (false) way, the confusion of the ego which guided us to the unknown, we encounter two types of games born from confusion:

- a) The game of the unknown, and
- b) The game of the unknown transcendent, both are part of the spiritual materialism.

Not knowing what or who we are, we still do know we want to be something or someone.

We decide to be what we would like to be, even if we do not know what it is, that is the first game (a). On top of that, besides our desire to be that (which we do not know what it is), we hope that such thing exists or is real in this universe! And this is how our desire is transformed in game b): the unknown transcendent.

This is what spiritual materialism is all about¹ and the danger is that under such influence many hypotheses are developed:

- Personal: because we want to be happy.
- Spiritual: we keep that huge discovery as a mystery
- and we accurately do not know what will happen when it is achieved as “absorption within the cosmos”, as it is vaguely described.
- If anybody would doubt this “absorption in the cosmos” we could either find new logical explanations which would take us further or find back up in spiritual or any other textbooks.

This would render our experience as “authentic”, leaving out any kind of doubt and set it in an unquestionable perspective which would call for the achievement of egoity rather than realization². At this point, those who won't accept it simply do not understand the ineffability of the spiritual and is their own fault for having no brains and no heart... (!)

2. The second path is to try to live accordingly to what we are.

In this second case, we shall investigate our confusion, suffering, pain, but not transform what we discover as answers to these problems. On the contrary, it is about going further and further, not looking for specific answers. It is about working with ourselves, our life, and our psyche, not looking for answers, simply observing things the way they are, in a simple and direct way, close to reality. If we can surrender to this process, an extraordinary opportunity opens for us, to make our confusion, our chaos and the neuroses of our minds the material of study, to work in ourselves. No event or personality trait is more important than other, or cause-effect of the other, so we reach the point where there are no more neither questions nor answers: both disappear. Therefore, there is no transcending hope. No-hope is the essence of Buddhist wisdom³.

The process consists in going further, deeper, with no spiritual reference, no good-evil parameters: just the basal level, not hopelessness but of no hope. This discovery process regenerates itself automatically enabling us to dig even deeper. This constant deepening process is the sole purpose that leads to wisdom.

This psychologic penetration process consists in transcending eight stages or aspects in which this buddhist wisdom is all about.

¹ Based on the fable of the donkey chasing the carrot.

² Every being is potentially Buddha.

³ It refers to *Samahdi* when the *bodhisattva* detaches from the last traces of the ego or dual thought.

This spirituality consists in going beyond our conceived “achievements” in the spiritual scope, because this “affirmation” would refrain our way forward, it becomes an obstacle. The spiritual path is a non-stop endless effort⁴.

Padmasambhava’s great teaching is that spirituality means transcending hope and fear, and discover at the same time, the great intelligence this requires: THIS is the doing of plain TRUTH: to experience totality.

Many times, we adjust things to the idea we have about them or to what we want to see of them, the difference of this approach lies in the wholesome precision that arises at the exact moment when things are seen, as they are.

TRIKAYA⁵

Padmasambhava’s method consists in overcoming what we have defined as spiritual materialism and develop primordial sanity. To cultivate primordial sanity means working on ourselves, and the main premise is the path itself rather than the achievement of a goal. It is the path itself that is a source of inspiration, not as in the story of the donkey and the carrot, not the promise of what we are going to get. Just to state the difference clearly, in spiritual materialism promises are like the carrot that calls the donkey to embark blindly in any sort of adventure. On the other hand, when spiritual materialism is overcome, there are no goals because they are present all the time, in all we live at every instant of our spiritual journey. This is the way the spiritual path turns beautiful and passionate as if we all were Buddhas offering messages, new discoveries, warnings. The path sends us to places by painful lessons and, also through joyous ones. To overcome spiritual materialism is a complete the voyage that depends not of an objective.

The fullness of this voyage is illustrated with Padmasambhava’s life. This plenitude is described by the sum of some elements such as the basic space or totality, the energy or game, and finally the practical application: the possibility to face the situations as they appear before us.

These are 3 principles:

- TOTALITY or the general context of the trip
- The notion of GAME
- The pragmatism to keep forward in the path

The path is a personal effort, the energy each of us invests in our daily living, to face our life either -creatively or destructively- as a learning process. Relating to “the other” is the constant game in our lives: it is the path, relating to reality one way or the other, or to unreality as you wish....

The process of living is the process of being, it is the path.

Life is constant change, we are never stuck, the path is neutral, no situation has precedence over another one. The truth is, the trip that started the moment of the original separation, when we began relating to reality in terms of ‘the other’, ‘I’, ‘mine’, ‘our’, etc. when we established a relationship with things as separate beings: This was the first creation of samsara and nirvana. At the very beginning we decided to relate somehow with the energy of the situations, thus we started the trip to travel the road. In time, we adopted a certain attitude towards the way and conditioned it by orienting it towards the worldly or the spiritual. In other words, spirituality, is not THE path, as such, but rather, a way of conditioning our trip and our energy. This conditioning intervenes, as

⁴ The six *paramitas* or transcendental practices of the bodhisattva, also called virtues or perfections. They are transcendental because they go beyond the ego. These are: generosity (*dana*), discipline (*shila*), patience (*kshanti*), effort (*virya*), meditation over the illusion of a separated individual ego (*dhyana*), knowledge that penetrates the ultimate reality of phenomenae and reaches vacuity (*prajñā*).

⁵ Chögyam Trungpa. Crazy Wisdom. Kairos, Barcelona,1994. p. 25.

the totality of our experience. This is the first category, one aspect of the road. The road is there anyway but we relate to it in a certain way and adopt a posture which determines if the path is worldly or spiritual for us. Thus, motivation arises. This motivation harbors 3 aspects of the path:

1. Dharmakaya
2. Sambhogakaya
3. Nirmanakaya

1. Dharmakaya

Gradually the path develops a determinate form sealed by a global attitude: fundamental sanity.

It is an ever-awake quality, not very attractive in the habitual sense: this total and complete openness enables to overcome hope and fear. Consequently, things are seen, as they are, and not as we want them to be. This fundamental sanity, this way of being that transcends hope and fear is the attitude of realization.

It is a very practical attitude (habit or capability) thanks to which we neither reject nor attach to those things that life endows us with. It is total openness, a total disposition to examine anything that arises, to work and relate with whatever comes up in the global context. This is **Dharmakaya**: the space that embraces all.

Every time we do not consider the world as an enemy, we adopt the **dharmakaya** criterion: the world is an opportunity, our work base. Not a something to fight against: the world is an extraordinarily rich situation that offers innumerable resources. Such fundamental generosity and total richness is **dharmakaya**: An absolute positive way of thinking.

2. Sambhogakaya

Things are open and manageable, but there is more...

We must relate to the energy and vivaciousness that includes passion, discovery, pride, jealousy etc. everything that appears to the mind as sparkling light which brightness crosses the depth of our path. This is the type of relationship we establish in our transit along the path, this is **sambhogakaya**.

Our transit along the path supposes a very intense passion and a total acceptance of things as they appear, as they are. This added element could be fascination for the passionate discoveries each situation unveils.

There is no need to classify such experiences as virtuous, vicious, religious, or worldly, we simply relate with what continually appears in the different situations of our life, such passions and feelings reveal new aspects of ourselves, which lead to a deeper discovery inside ourselves. This turns things very interesting, at the end, we are not so plain and empty as we might have thought.

3. Nirmanakaya

This is the pragmatic aspect of our life. In one side, we have totality and in the other a variety of energies, besides there is a way to live IN the world as it is but this implies a certain discipline: it demands a great effort and surveillance. All the traditional techniques that usually describe spiritual practices, such as meditation, working with the mind, to deepen inside relationships, to develop fundamental compassion and a sense of communication, to cultivate knowledge, to acquire the wisdom to appreciate situations in their totality and turn what is happening into a manageable experience. All these disciplines are **nirmanakaya**.

These 3 stages: Dharmakaya, Sambhogakaya and Nirmanakaya joined together are the basis of our spiritual journey. Thanks to them our journey and our attitude turn operative: it is something we

can manage in an intelligent and direct way with no need to make any reference to “the mystery of life” or any other vague category.

In the psychological scope, each one of these principles has characteristics worth mentioning: **Dharmakaya** is the fundamental entity in which confusion or ignorance have never existed nor requires any point of reference.

Sambhogakaya is a state that always contain spontaneous energy, since it never depends on any cause/effect-conditioned type of energy.

Nirmanakaya is a self-existent plenitude where there is no need to create strategies to function.

These are the psychological traits that manifest in the Buddhist state, each one of us must work with these principles: To be a Buddha is a way of being, not a goal. Inner work is developed inside out, the mask falls by itself, when each one of us is relentless, we cannot be deceived, and will not mistake the way: when we are completely open-minded, awake, nothing can induce us onto blind territory. It is as fire, the fire does not “possess” its destructive nature, destruction simply occurs when it is there, if we interfere with the nature of the elements or passion *phenomenae*, for this matter, with irreverence or sloppiness, these act according to their nature.

PRIMAL INNOCENCE

The discovery of the path and the right attitude towards it, play an important role in the spiritual scope, because the path opens the possibility to relate with our inner self, our primordial or innocent being.

Nonetheless, we give so much importance to pain and confusion that we forget the primal innocence.

What we generally do is to find in spirituality an experience that enables us to discover ourselves as adults instead of connecting with our infant innocence. Deceived, we look for something that enables us to be “respectable adults”, or psychologically stable.

The deceit consists in that we think a realized person should behave as an old sage, either as an old professor (!), or as an aged father who can wisely advice over how to face all life’s problems or an old grandmother who knows all the recipes and remedies.

The teachings of the tantra show another sort of realization, linked to innocence and youthfulness, the awoken state cannot not be described as “old or adult” but rather as young and free state. In other words, youth and freedom flow from the awoken state. The awoken state resembles a dawn: something fresh and vivacious, wakeful. The spiritual path always entrails new, fresh discoveries. Life beats and confuses us, however there are people who can cross turbulent waters and find answers, that strive enormously to reach serenity, this is what Buddhism understands for the awoken-state, it is an astonishing message: we are capable of realization being as a child: if we are awake we are pure creatures, we are innocent for we have returned to our original being.

We have the capacity to discover our inner child’s innocence and beauty, those princely aspects of ourselves. At the encounter with our confusion and neuroses, we find they are harmless and innocuous, after we gradually discover our childlike innocence. It is about discovering the child we have inside and become curious, spontaneous and vivacious to know life, and the world, better. We start to enlighten as a rebirth in pure innocence and eternal youth.

Our experience of duality, what we thought we knew, our preconceived ideas, all turns false and crumbles down so we acknowledge the real dimension of the path. This enables us to abandon our egotic mistrust or at least be aware of its existence.

The more conscious we are of the ego and its neuroses, the closer we get to that childlike state where we do not know how to take the next step in life. It's a rediscovery of perception from zero, a rediscovery of things as they are really.

Padmasambhava's life illustrates in a very simple manner this concepts:

He was born from a gigantic lotus in the lake Dhanakosha at Uddinaya, in today's Himalayan Afghanistan. He was curious, joyful and vivacious. As he had not been touched by anything, he was no afraid of touching anything.

He was driven by king Indrabhadra's gardeners to the palace and was enthroned prince by the marveled King. He was named Padma Raja –*Pema Gyalpo*- in Tibetan language, which means King of the Lotus.

His childhood represents this childlike state of plenitude where there is no duality, matched by a condition of freshness for it is a state of totality, limitless with no points of reference. As there are no points of reference, there is nothing that could tarnish ideas or concepts: It is one whole, perfect unbroken totality.

After he married, he became playful and experimented with his aggression and discovered that his strength enabled him to toss and break objects. This playfulness in its full expression led him to know his wisdom. Once, he danced in the rooftop letting fall a vajra and a trident which killed a mother and her son who were passing by. He went too far in his playful attempt to explore the world, attitude which situates this happening in the sambhokakaya scope where experiences are lived with all its subtleties and go through birth and death as well. The king had to banish him, the phenomonic world is extremely legalist and governed by cause-effect relationships. The lesson was to learn about the legality of karma, about the karmic interactions of the external world, the world of confusion. It was precisely the world of confusion that made of him a teacher. The child-like exploratory attitude that is developed in us when we walk the spiritual path, demands to work with perils and pleasures of all sorts. This child-like attitude tends to expand into the outer world since the instant realization state, acquired by the relationships we build, is not the end but the beginning of the journey. Suddenly, we experience an awakening instant, and then, we become children; from there, we explore how to work with phenomenae, dance with them, and relate to persons who are sunk in confusion. The relationship with confused beings, makes us take certain attitudes depending on the sort of teachings these beings might need and the kind of situations that should be created to establish meaningful relationships with them.

So, Darmakhaya is the great space where to move, such as the sea. Sambhokakaya is the energy, or passion within it, such as the waves. And Nirmanakaya is like the ship on it, thanks to which the whole situation becomes manageable and operative and we can travel through the ocean. Confusion is the other side of the coin, as (human) comprehension has its own limits, it is always present until the whole situation is understood and we and need no more help.

When we work with totality we have the fundamental space needed to work in life, as we also have the energy and pragmatism. Part of the frustration we experience comes from the impression that we do not have enough resources to transform our vital situation and improvise with it, but, these three principles -dharmakaya, sambhokakaya and nirmanakaya- offer limitless improvisation resources.

The vajra with which the baby passing by the palace was killed represents the skillful means, and the trident that went into the mother's heart represents wisdom. He represents aggression while she represents ignorance: the two elements which intertwine to form confusion.

Padmasambhava's story is a practical manual for Buddhas, and each one of us is a Buddha.

This story is told from Padmasambhava's inner (gnoseologic) experience, managing skillfully the situations which have been created for us, what we simply should do is go out and surrender to them, it seems a puzzle with a life of its own that builds itself. Hope and fear must vanish before the dance starts, the absence of aggression transforms into energy, distortions transform into wisdom: it all transmutes.

The need of a teacher is to lead us towards the first step only.

ETERNITY AND CREMATION GROUND.

After Padmasambhava reached the awaken state, experienced sexuality, aggression and all the pleasures of the world, he was still not clear how to link this up with this worldly processes.

This uncertainty is not fear, he needed to discover how to teach, how to bond with those who would listen to him. To work with an illuminated one can be subtle and agreeable but extremely dangerous, it could be destructive, like playing with fire.

In this endeavor to communicate with the *samsaric*⁶ mind, he discovers ETERNITY.

Eternity is thus understood as the awaken state, without fluctuations, where no decisions need to be taken. From there, and in relation to the second aspect, this "not-decision-taking" is Padmasambhava's fore relationship with the sentient beings.

This second aspect is called *Vajradhara*: the principle or psychological state of lack of fear. Because fear of death, pain, or misfortune have been previously transcended. Nevertheless, eternity goes further. This concept applies to our own life and does not resemble the general idea most people have about it: it encompasses a sensation of continuity, because it has transcended the fear of birth, death, illness and pain. He feels lively, electrically and continually that it is not himself who is alive and living but the whole world: so, He is the World and the World is Him. That is the experience of BEING as such: UNITY.

Vajradhara is a sanscrit word. *Vajra* means indestructible, and *dhara* owner, so it means the possessor of indestructibility or the possessor of immobility. Therefore, he does not perceive the world as a menace but as his home, that is how he achieved the primordial state of eternity, which has nothing to do with the idea of perpetuation of the ego which is always trying to find new ways of displaying itself in search of security.

This is the way Padmasambhava acquired the permanent state of eternity inspired by the sentient beings sunk in confusion. Through the observation of the impermanence of life, he discovered eternity in life: the constant and changing succession of birth and death. This he could see living in a cremation ground full of corpses and decay: birth, death and chaos. We bump all the time in our every-day life with situations that resemble this crematory field... Such chaos may be a source of inspiration until it transforms somehow in a sort of order. When it transforms in an ordered chaos it ceases to be confusing and enables us to relate with the world as it is. Padmasambhava went into a cave to meditate over the eternity of the buddhic nature: Buddhic nature is eternal and cannot be altered. This is the first stage a *vidyadhara* must step into: The bigger the chaos is, the more transformation of such situations in ornaments that we will undergo. Such an experience needs not an education: it is the innate nature built within us.

The idea that learning is needed to face the world is very weakening because we feel we do not have within us what it takes, that we must strive to be better and that we should compete with heroes or teachers to "imitate" that which we are not. But when that spark of illumination happens,

⁶ *Samsara* stands for the vicious circle of confusion.

this error shatters and we no longer shall pretend: We Are. Anyhow, many of the inclinations we are born with shall only be set free to manifest in the every-day course of our lives.

We cannot cheat with our experiences, we cannot modify them with our thoughts either.

In a very unrealistic way, we may think things will turn out fine and that everything will be alright at the end. That is exactly what is NOT going to happen. That is facing things mistakenly, because in the world of opposites nothing can be achieved: beauty opposes ugliness and pleasure to pain. A precasted faith can only render a momentary enthusiasm: we must plunge into life's troubles and build a home in there: pain plays no role here it turns into something we can relate with. It is each one of us who must build our path to unity.

This is Padmasambhava's new adaptation to the world through the attitude of eternity.

This is the most precise knowledge of how to encounter the different situations. With no ideals or strategies, we only need to be OPEN and be in harmony with the elements.

LET THE PHENOMENAE PLAY.

I shall attempt to exemplify all aspects of Padmasambhava's teachings, which will be hard since words are not an adequate means to get to the its intimate, embryonic and instantaneous point of relationship with life in this dimension, sort of a precognitive aspect of his teachings.

The "inner" story of his biography displays this attempt. First as a prince, then as a young *siddha* in the crematory field. The next step is to be accepted as a *bhikshu* or monk in a monastery this would add discipline to his character: He was ordered by Ananda, Budha's personal disciple as *Shakya Senge* (Lion of the *Shakya* tribe) which identified his lineage with the Budhic tradition, which main trait is a fundamental and constant sanity, a healthy way to face life because it consists in fusing with things as they are (and not as we wish them to be). And so, he decided to save the world through the message of *dharma*.

He lived those days with rigor, but at the same time he was willing to let others make mistakes in the spiritual path, as for example, let a king burn him alive, or throw his own daughter to a thorn ditch. He thought it pedagogically necessary to let those things happen, because mistakes enable us to be conscious of our own neuroses and our general (erratic) way of thinking. Such consciousness should be achieved without external influence.

This is an important indication of how Padmasambhava related to the samsaric confused mind: he let the confusion manifest and then correct itself: **LET THE PHENOMENAE PLAY.**

Let them make fool of themselves, that is the way to proceed. There is no use in "let me speak to...", "...want to explain the situation point by point..." the act of saying something is simply not enough, not to mention the difficulty of finding the exact words... It is of no use. We cannot fool the phenomenic world with words, or drawing upon logic, an inconsequential logic. We can only relate to the phenomenic world in terms of what happens within itself, in terms of its own logic. It is a wider concept than logic itself, where the global situation is considered.

An important trait of Padmasambhava's teachings is to let the phenomenae unfold until they play out, instead of demonstrating or explaining anything.

The next situation comes forth when Padmasambhava encounters a group of sages called *tirthikas* in the sanskrit language, in this case they were brahmans but could have been Jehova's followers or any other theistic tradition opposed to the non-theistic buddhadharma approach. In a debate the theistic sage argued against the non-theistic *pandit* over the nature of spirituality. Both had a spiritual fixation, both trying to secure their own spiritual path as the single stagnant, correct one. Even though the theistic sage won, Padmasambhava was called to celebrate a destruction ceremony, which he did destroying it all, including the ashram. Under this aspect he is known as

*Senge Drádrok*⁷. The lion's roar destroys the dualistic psychology in which the existence of things rest upon the existence of a God Brahma or any other. This forked point of view arises problems all the time. From a Buddhist perspective this "other" does not exist and the reason is that "this" (the self) has ceased to exist. It is a mutual destruction which favors the non-theistic view point: If Brahma or Jehova existed, he who perceives him would have to exist also, to recognize His existence. Buddhism sustains that he who could recognize such Existence does not exist, or at least his existence is disputable (due to its contingency). So, if this does not exist the "Other" does not either. He is only a ghost of the imagination. And for an image to exist there should be someone that imagines. Therefore, the destruction of the central notion of the self leads to the inexistence of "that other".

The lion's roar is heard because he does not fear "the other".

This aspect is related to the *Vajra pride*. Known as *Dorje Trolö* when he arrived to Tibet.

Tibetan's ancestral *Pön* tradition had no external gods, it rested upon the adoration of "the absolute" or *yeshen*, the primordial, the ancestral, big friend or celestial. So, solving this through logic was not an option due to the deepness of the approach. This primordial approach is similar to the original American, Shinto and Taoist traditions, which are extraordinarily sensible perspectives.

But all of them too anthropocentric, by setting men as the center of the universe, they do not follow the fundamental continuity of consciousness. Proof of it, is the sacrifice of living beings in the core of their cults.

It is surprisingly difficult to spread a non-theistic approach in a primitive country where theistic ideas have rooted, because the relationship of its inhabitants to the land which has fed them, and the sky which has sheltered them, cradles a very strong veneration.

The Buddhist tradition is not about a god against another god. It has no god to substitute any other god. The only substitute is wisdom: the mind is very powerful, and everyone has a mind, even animals do. Our state of mind is very powerful. We can accomplish everything we intend in the mental plane: we have an infinite capacity to create and destroy.

Everything we have created is to demonstrate ourselves –and the others- that we exist!

It is humanistic approach: The human being exists, His intelligence exists. This is a non-theistic affirmation. And **MAGIC** is situated precisely in this plane

Everything that happens occurs in this earthly plane in a very direct and practical way: this is *Dorje Trolö's* wisdom: it pervades everything, it is simple there.

Dorje Trolö ignores any conventional logic, he just guides himself with one logic: to relate to the earth and the sky: both are limitless.

He even thought, these ideas might be of use in the future so, he hid some of them in the mountains of Tibet for the benefit of future generations: Pure spiritual energy, if we can see it directly we are absolutely present, this is the great pride: the simultaneous impact of wisdom and compassion, with no possibility of analysis: it is either **THERE** or it is not!

Vajra pride is the perception that the fundamental sanity is within us, and therefore, there is no need to deduce its existence through logic: we do not have to demonstrate that something happens or does not happen. The profound dissatisfaction that makes us go in search of spiritual awareness is a *Vajra's* pride expression.

⁷ Lion's roar.

Cynicism and Devotion.

At this point, the general image of Padmasambhava has been displayed.

There are 3 approaches to read this story:

- The external: based on facts
- The inner: or psychological
- The superior or secret: that corresponds to wisdom.

I have concentrated in this last one, the wise approach, incorporating some elements of the other two. If Padmasambhava is a cosmic principle, rather than a historic character, how can we relate to him?

The different manifestations of this cosmic principle arise continuously: as *Shakya Senge*, *Ñima Öser*, *Pema Gyalpo*, *Dorje Trolö*, and some others. Padmasambhava, as a principle, contains all the elements that are part of realization.

A safe method is always an attitude of mistrust: towards ourselves, the teachings, and the teacher. We should consider it with certain reserve, examine it, and test all its details, this attitude assures sincerity and exposes self-deception which is of utmost importance, since spirituality cannot be attained from spiritual materialism.

From mistrustfulness, a different and opposite focus is opened: true cynicism (such as a *Vajra*) and cultivated in the *Vajra* nature. Even though it is referred to as extraordinary, it is totally common and ordinary.

To understand this, we shall probably need to change some of our ways:

- to cultivate devotion and faith: that is, some warmth in our hearts.
- to remove self-deceit through sincerity

and therefore, create a positive ground to acquire a positive understanding of ourselves, the teachings and the teacher. To work with this cosmic principle of elemental sanity, a certain romanticism –**BHAKTI**– is also needed.

BHAKTI may be expressed in two ways:

- a) As a feeling of poverty.

The individual has the impression that he is missing something the everyone else has, and thus, admires “that” which he lacks: could be the aim, the guru, the teachings... with such an attitude of poverty all those things seem marvelous because he does not have them, this attitude branches out of the spiritual materialism, and derives essentially from a lack of sanity, and a lack of self-confidence and sense of a lack of richness or abundance.

- b) The second type of romantic (wholesome) attitude comes from the feeling that the self has something, that there “is something” already there in one’s own heart. We value what we truly are. Each one of us has as much as the teacher has. And as everyone is following the dharma’s path, there is no need to look at the path from the outside: this is a healthy, and fundamentally rich approach, in which the feeling of poverty simply does not fit.

This sort of romanticism is important: it is the greatest force there is:

- It destroys cynicism which only protects and perpetuates itself.
- It dismantles the ego’s cynical game to open the way to a better and greater *vajra* pride.

Thus, a sense of beauty arises, even a sense of LOVE and light.

Without this full scope, the relationship with the principle of Padmasambhava is only an attempt of measuring the deepness of another psychological experience, still a myth, something one does not own. Therefore, will seem interesting but won’t become personal: devotion and compassion is the only way to grace or *Padmasambhava’s adhishtana*.

Being cynical and skeptical could be an honest way to relate to “the other” which also encompasses ourselves, by the way. But there comes a moment where not only this coldness but also warmth is essential.

This is a logical explanation within the conceptual mind, somehow expressed with words. But in fact it is so warm, strong and magnetic that can be shocking.

Clearly, the study of Padmasambhava is a milestone in the common journey we have undertaken, therefore, it is time to practice this healthy romantic attitude. The opportunity to talk about Padmasambhava is a very fortunate and exceptional incident. The opportunities to speak about this matters are extremely rare, unique and valuable. Nevertheless, this type of exceptional and valuable opportunities occur constantly. In fact, our life, as part of the teachings, is something precious. This is the reason, why dharma⁸ is precious: Human life has a unique value.

Each one of us has a brain, sensory perceptions, and therefore, material to work with: Each one of us has had problems in the past –depressions, struggles, moments of despair and madness- and all of it, eventually makes sense.

And so, the journey continues and the chance⁹ we concur here today does too. This is the type of romanticism or warmth I refer to. It is worth engaging with the teachings with this healthy principle.

Such is the way to relate with the principle of Padmasambhava, to Buddhist teachings.

⁸ The *dharma* (path) is *one's self*, and we are always *in it*.

⁹ Free will is the cause of casuality. Without free will there could be no accidents. Casuality is karma. Everything is sudden and karmatic at once: ignorance is an accident, duality is an accident, it is a great misunderstanding.